

TRAINING AS A PANACEA TO JOB PERFORMANCE. A STUDY OF SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN OGUN STATE. NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Job performance among university lecturers has always been a major challenge. This paper therefore explores training as a panacea to job performance. A study of selected universities in Ogun State using the descriptive survey design. A sample of 363 lecturers was selected through the stratified random sampling technique. Instruments used for data collection were the Demographic Data Inventory (DDI) and Training and Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). Three hypotheses were formulated and tested by means of the simple linear regression analysis at the .05 level of significance. Results revealed a significant influence of training on teaching quality ($\beta = .267, t = 14.006, p < .0005$), research productivity ($\beta = .203, t = 12.174, p < .0005$) and performance of administrative tasks ($\beta = .187, t = 9.317, p < .0005$) among university lecturers in Ogun State. It was subsequently recommended, among other things, that universities should prioritize and invest in comprehensive training and development initiatives for lecturers.

Keywords: *training, panacea, job performance, teaching quality, research productivity*

Introduction

Job performance among university lecturers has always been a major challenge. It is believed that employee's job performance is crucial and instrumental to the growth, profitability and achievement to organizational objectives. Job performance among university lecturers is a topic of great significance, as it directly impacts the quality of education and academic outcomes. Ogun State, located in Nigeria, is known for its thriving higher educational institutions. The state is known for its significant number of universities, making it an appropriate area of focus for this study. Understanding the factors that influence job performance among university lecturers in Ogun State is crucial for improving educational standards and fostering professional growth.

According to Ojo (2019), job performance is a multidimensional phenomenon whose elements include effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, quality and behaviour. It is clear that when workers' skills, attitude and knowledge are improved upon, it leads to efficient and

effective delivery on the job. Job performance has been found to predict important outcomes for individuals and organizations. Understanding the complexities of job performance is vital for organizations to effectively manage and enhance employee productivity and organizational success.

University education can, therefore, be considered a platform on which the future development of a nation rests (Hassan, 2017). According to Hassan (2015), university in Nigeria was established to create and spread knowledge and skills among students and other members of the societies. To attain this goal, there is need for adequate and efficient staff. Thus, it is crucial to train and develop staff in order to adapt to the new dynamism in technology in achieving the stated goals of university education. Training is at the heart of employee utilization, commitment, improved productivity, motivation and growth, and very essential for improved organizational productivity. The effect of staff training and development on employee's productivity and job performance has attracted considerable interest in analytical and empirical literature. Employee's training and development has been recognized as a crucial part of any competent management (Stephen, 2020). Staff development or human resource development refers to the improvement in knowledge, skills, attitudes and endowment of the labour force so as to bring about sustainable economic growth.

Training is very vital to job productivity and organizational performance. While few individuals may have the requisite skills, knowledge, abilities and competencies needed to fit into a specific job function, some others may require extensive training to acquire the necessary skills to be able to fit in a specific job function and also make significant contribution to the organization's performance. Lack of staff training and development may therefore lead to failure in accomplishing defined task.

Onasanya (2015) asserts that staff development as a form of specialized education aimed at giving the employee a particular or specialized knowledge, skill and attitude which he must possess to effectively perform in a given position while development is concerned with specific programmes designed to prepare and groom a worker with particular education and training for higher responsibilities. For instance, in the universities, there is need for a continuous and regular involvement by academic and non-academic personnel in staff development programmes that will enhance their skills and knowledge in order to be effective and efficient in task delivery. Such programmes include seminars, workshops among others.

Training is critical for enhancing employee competencies and capabilities, directly influencing job performance. In the context of universities, where the quality of education and research output heavily relies on faculty performance, investigating the impact of training and development on job performance becomes imperative. Chênevert, Vandenberghe, and Doucet (2020) observe that universities are increasingly operating in a competitive environment where attracting and retaining talented faculty members is crucial. Effective training and development programmes can serve as a strategic tool for universities to enhance faculty job satisfaction, productivity and ultimately, the competitive advantage of the institution. Research by Aggarwal and Thakur (2020) emphasizes the positive relationship between employee job performance and organizational effectiveness. By investigating the determinants of job performance, particularly

staff training and development, this study contributes to the understanding of factors influencing the overall effectiveness and success of universities in Ogun State.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and will be tested in this study.

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of training on teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of training on research productivity among university lecturers in Ogun State.

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of training on performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Methods

Design and Participants

This study adopted the descriptive survey design which enabled the researcher to collect data from a cross-section of the target population without manipulating the predictor variable (staff training and development) but measuring them as they pre-exist among the participants. The population of the study comprises of all the 5,930 academic staff of both the private and public universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. A sample of 375 lecturers, determined by the Taro Yamane's formula, was selected through the stratified random sampling technique.

Instrumentation

The instruments used for data collection in this study included Demographic Data Inventory (DDI) that measured type of university, gender, age, rank and work experience and a questionnaire, and a questionnaire titled "Staff Training and Development and Job Performance Questionnaire" (STDJPQ). The STDJPQ consists of 37 items in a 4-point Likert scale format. It has two sections. The first section measures Job Performance, while the second section measures Staff Training and Development. The Job Performance sub-scale consists of 20 items, while the Training sub-scale consists of 15 items. The response format on this instrument ranges from 1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree. Sample items on the scale include the following:

- *Actively engaging students in the learning process during lectures and classes.*
- *The university does not provide financial support or grants for staff to pursue further education or professional certifications.*

A pilot test was carried out using test–retest method of reliability assessment by administering the instruments on 20 respondents from one public and one private Universities (Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode and Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo respectively) at interval of two weeks to determine the stability of the items constituting the questionnaire. The responses of these 20 respondents on both occasions were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. The correlation coefficient obtained from the instruments yielded 0.73 and 0.76 for Job Performance sub-scale and Staff Training and Development sub-scale respectively. These reliability coefficients indicate that the reliability of the instrument is substantial and good enough for use for this study. In order to ascertain the content validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was given to three other experts in the fields of personnel psychology, management science and test and measurement for scrutiny and vetting. These experts made valuable corrections and suggestions which were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument.

Method of Data Analysis

The demographic data of participants were analyzed by means of frequency counts and percentage. Each of the hypotheses was tested using simple linear regression analysis at the .05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of training n teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Table 1: Coefficients of the Simple Linear Regression Analysis for Influence of Training on Teaching Quality

	B	Std Error	β	T	Sig.
(Constant)	9.416	4.362		21.042	.000
Staff training and development	.119	.0184	.267	14.006	.000

Dependent Variable: Teaching Quality

Table 1 revealed significant results ($\beta = .267$, $t = 14.006$, $p < .0005$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant influence of staff training and development on teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of training on research productivity among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Table 2: Coefficients of the Simple Linear Regression Analysis for Influence of Training on Research Productivity

	B	Std Error	β	T	Sig.
(Constant)	5.783	5.185		21.042	.000
Staff training and development	.126	.016	.203	12.174	.000

Dependent Variable: Research Productivity

Table 2 revealed significant results ($\beta = .203$, $t = 12.174$, $p < .0005$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant influence of staff training and development on research productivity among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant influence of training on performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Table 3: Coefficients of the Simple Linear Regression Analysis for Influence of Training on Performance of Administrative Tasks

	B	Std Error	β	t	Sig.
(Constant)	10.581	3.447		21.042	.000
Staff training and development	.142	.022	.187	9.317	.000

Dependent Variable: Performance of Administrative Tasks

Table 3 revealed significant results ($\beta = .187$, $t = 9.317$, $p < .0005$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant influence of training on performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Discussion:

The outcome of this study revealed that the majority of respondents performed their jobs well and at a high level. This implied that there might be additional elements, such as school motivation and tone that improve lecturers' job performance. Ghalawat, Kiran & Kumari (2020) discovered that the majority of teachers are highly productive in their teaching, which lends credence to this study. Since the main goal of teaching is to bring about desired change in learners, the study also found that using effective teaching methods results in better performance from students. According to the study, secondary school teachers use a variety of instructional strategies to encourage students to learn. Research suggests that using a combination of instructional methods, including lectures, discussions, cooperative learning, hands-on activities, and technology integration, can enhance student engagement.

The study's findings showed that university lecturers at a few chosen universities in Ogun State, Nigeria, had a good degree of training and development. From this, it can be concluded in general that university lecturers have good, encouraging, and satisfactory levels of training and development. According to Habib, Zahra & Mushtaq (2015) training boosts self-efficacy and improves job performance. Thus, this study lend support to that of Ibrahim, Boerhannoeddin, & Bakare (2017) who reported that training helps staff members develop better abilities, attitudes, and knowledge to perform better. Enhancing employee knowledge, skills, abilities, competencies, and behavior through training has been demonstrated to benefit organizations and employees by improving performance.

Summary

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the impact of training on various aspects of job performance among university lecturers in selected universities in Ogun State.

Conclusion

Firstly, the study found a significant positive influence of training on teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State. This implies that when lecturers undergo training programmes, they are better equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills and resources to deliver high-quality teaching. This finding underscores the importance of investing in continuous professional development for educators to enhance the overall educational experience for students.

Secondly, another significant finding of the study is the positive impact of training on research productivity among university lecturers. This suggests that training initiative not only contribute to improved teaching quality but also stimulate research output among academic staff. By providing opportunities for research-focused training and skill development, universities can foster a culture of innovation and academic excellence, thereby enhancing their research capabilities and scholarly output.

Finally, the study revealed a significant positive influence of training on the performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers. Effective administrative skills are essential for managing academic responsibilities, coordinating activities and ensuring efficient operation of academic departments or units. By investing in training programmes that target administrative skills development, universities can enhance the overall efficiency and effectiveness of their academic operations. In a nutshell, these findings highlight the multifaceted benefits of training initiative in the context of higher education institutions. By investing in continuous learning and professional growth opportunities for academic staff, universities in Ogun State can not only improve teaching quality and research productivity but also enhance administrative performance, ultimately contributing to the overall advancement and success of the institutions. Furthermore, these findings underscore the importance of incorporating training and development programmes as integral components of institutional strategies aimed at enhancing job performance and fostering a conducive environment for academic excellence.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made/

Universities should prioritize and invest in comprehensive training initiative for staff. This programme should be designed to address the specific needs and challenges faced by academic staff in their respective roles. Furthermore, universities should consider expanding the range of training offerings to cover a broad spectrum of topics, including pedagogical techniques, research methodologies, academic writing, time management and leadership skills.

Universities should foster a supportive environment that encourages continuous learning and professional growth among academic staff. This can be achieved by establishing mechanisms for ongoing assessment of training needs, providing access to diverse learning opportunities, such as workshops, seminars, conferences, online courses and mentoring programmes. Additionally, universities should recognize and reward faculty members who actively engage in professional development activities and demonstrate improvements in teaching, research and administrative performance as a result.

To ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of training effort, universities should integrate this initiative into their institutional policies and practices. This may involve incorporating training requirements into faculty development plans, allocating dedicated resources for training programmes in the annual budget and establishing clear guidelines for evaluating the impact of training on job performance. Moreover, universities should involve academic staff in the decision-making process regarding the development and implementation of training initiatives to ensure relevance and acceptance from stakeholders.

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